

Research Assessment at the MDC

This survey gathers scientific group leaders' and technology platform leaders' perspectives to inform the "Establish Research Assessment & Monitoring Practices" strategic action of the MDC2030 project.

It should take approximately **10 minutes** to finish it.

There are 19 questions in this survey.

Biographical and professional profile

Your position is *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Tenured (permanent)
- Non-tenured

You are a *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Scientific Group Leader
- Technology Platform Leader

You identify as *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer to not respond

How many team members does your group have? *

Please write your answer here:

How many Postdoctoral scientists are currently in your team?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0
- 1 - 2
- 3 - 5
- > 5

How many PhD students are currently in your team?

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0
- 1 - 2
- 3 - 5
- > 5

How many Master students do you regularly supervise? Please give an estimate sum throughout a year

Please write your answer here:

How many years have you been a group leader / platform leader at the MDC? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0 - 5
- 6 - 10
- 11 - 15
- > 15

Were you group leader / platform leader before joining MDC? If so, how many years? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No, I was not
- 0 -5
- 6 - 10
- 11 - 15
- > 15

Time allocation

How you allocate your time in a **regular work week**?

We will use the normalised difference between current and desired time allocation to understand the value alignment between the needs of the institute and the individual ones.

Please choose whether you would like to estimate your time in hours or percentages

We would recommend to use hours.

If you use percentages, please take into account all sections to calculate them. If they don't add up to 100 we will scale them.

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Hours
- Percentages

Research activities & outputs:

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

	Current time allocation per week	Optimal time allocation per week
Conducting research (wet lab, data analysis, etc)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Writing (papers & review articles)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Writing grants	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Grant / Project Management (reporting, budgeting)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Collaboration-building, Consortium Work & Team Science (including both internal and external collaborations)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Participating in Open Science practices (directly or promoting them in your team - includes producing and managing open software)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Scientific dissemination (invited lectures, conference participation)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Education & talent management:

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

	Current time allocation per week	Optimal time allocation per week
Teaching engagements	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Mentoring and supervision of Scientific staff (students & Postdocs, please include also the unofficial mentoring you do for early career researchers of other labs)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Supervision and management of Technical & Administrative Staff	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
PhD defense / TAC meetings (take into account also time reviewing the theses and students' reports)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Hiring and reviewing applications (both for your own group and for positions open at the institute)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Innovation & entrepreneurship:

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

	Current time allocation per week	Optimal time allocation per week
Patenting activities	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Collaborations with industry partners (board memberships, projects, etc)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Innovation grants	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Spin-off and start-up projects (funding, participating in board, etc)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Translation:

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

	Current time allocation per week	Optimal time allocation per week
Developing and running clinical trials	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Participating in patient engagement activities	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Drug development & repurposing (if it's not the main research area of the lab)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Ethics and regulatory committees activities	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Scientific community - internal and external:

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

	Current time allocation per week	Optimal time allocation per week
Participating in research management (POF / Strategy writing, policymaking, participation to SAB and similar boards - internal or external)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Organising lecture series, conferences, & workshops	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Reviewing papers, grants, & editorial duties	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Participating in scientific societies	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Championing Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Peer mentoring (not team members!)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Public community:

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

	Current time allocation per week	Optimal time allocation per week
Public outreach and citizen science activities (ie Long Night of Science, Berlin Science Week, ...)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Participating in green and sustainable initiatives	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

A citizen science example is FoldIt, an online game developed by researchers at the University of Washington in 2008. It invited anyone to solve puzzles related to protein folding. Players manipulated virtual structures to achieve the most energetically stable conformations, and the best solutions were analyzed by scientists to improve computational models of protein structure prediction. The project gained international recognition when players helped determine the crystal structure of a retroviral protease from the Mason-Pfizer monkey virus, a problem that had puzzled scientists for over a decade (<https://doi.org/10.1038/nsmb.2119>)

Personal development:

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

	Current time allocation per week	Optimal time allocation per week
Professional development (workshops and courses)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Answering surveys	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

**Is there any activity not listed on which you spend significant amount of your time and/or would like to spend a significant amount of your time?
If so please estimate time for these as well.**

Please write your answer here:

Reflections

We are happy to hear any additional comments on the survey and on the topic of Research Assessment:

Please write your answer here:

Thank you for your time and valuable input.

Your feedback will play an important role in supporting the “Establish Research Assessment & Monitoring Practices” strategic action and will help shape fair, inclusive, and forward-looking evaluation practices at our institute.

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Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.